

Data set of measurement data vs test conditions for IT performance characterised in presence of separate and combined influence factors

Partner	UNIBO
Measured power quality parameter	Amplitudes of the Harmonics
Influence factor 1	Temperature
Influence factor 2 (if combined with 1)	Humidity
Influence factor 3 (if combined with 2 and 3)	-
Index used to compare the reference power quality parameter with the measured power quality parameter	Harmonic ratio error defined as $\varepsilon_h = 100 \cdot \frac{k_n U_{s,h} - I_{p,h}}{I_{p,h}}$
Transducer under test	<p>Three Rogowski coils (LPCTs):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LPCT number 1 (ROG1) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rated primary current ±1 kA - Output voltage (at 50 Hz) 85 mV/kA - Accuracy class 0.5 • LPCT number 2 (ROG2) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rated primary current ±1 kA - Output voltage (at 50 Hz) 100 mV/kA - Accuracy class 0.5 • LPCT number 3 (ROG3) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rated primary current ±1 kA - Output voltage (at 50 Hz) 100 mV/kA - Accuracy class 0.5
Measurement procedure (short description)	<p>A representation of the temperature cycle accuracy test, aimed at assessing the effects of temperature, is reported in Figure 1.</p> <p align="center"><i>Fig 1: Temperature cycle accuracy test</i></p> <p>The temperature cycle accuracy test is chosen taking into consideration IEC 61869-6:2016. The temperature variation rate between any two temperature values is set at 0.1 °C/min. After reaching the test temperature, this value is</p>

maintained for 3 hours to achieve thermal stability and then the measurements are performed at the different test temperatures: (i) 20 °C, (ii) 40 °C, (iii) -5 °C, (iv) 20 °C. In the first temperature cycle accuracy test, the humidity is set at 30%. Then, an equivalent temperature cycle accuracy test is performed at 80%.

-Current waveforms:

During the four data acquisition window of Figure 1, the three LPCTs under test are supplied with the following test waveforms:

- single-tone sinusoidal waveforms summarized in Table I,

h	$I_{h,RMS}$
1	100
3	50
5	50
7	50
11	50
13	50
17	50
25	36
50	36

- sinc waveforms of 50 Hz.

For all waveforms, the acquisition window is set at 1 s. Therefore, the frequency resolution is 1 Hz. The sampling frequency is 50 kSa/s.

A brief description of the test procedure is provided below: the three Rogowski coils under test (RUTs) are placed inside a controlled temperature and humidity chamber. The RUTs are centered on the conductor.

In case of sine wave, the primary current is generated by a calibrator and then amplified by a transconductance, whereas, in case of sinc signal, a function generator substitutes for the calibrator.

Measurement Setup (short description)

A schematic block diagram of generation and measurement setup is represented in Figure 2.

Fig 2: Generation and measurement setup

For the generation, a Fluke transconductance transforms into a current $i_p(t)$ and amplifies a voltage signal produced by the Fluke calibrator or an arbitrary function generator (AWG) depending on type of signal. In particular, the calibrator creates the sine waves, whereas the AWG creates the sinc waveforms.

To measure the current provided to the three RUTs, a reference shunt resistor is used.

For data acquisition, a NI DAQ 9238 is employed. The acquisition system is used to acquire four different signals: the output of the three RUTs and the output of the reference shunt.

Main results (tables, plots,...)

Results of the test are provided in Figure 3 where three curves are reported. The blue curve is the harmonic ratio error response measured in presence of combined influence factors. The red curve refers to the case of adjacent phases energized. The black line is the harmonic ratio error measured in presence of the sole proximity effect.

Fig 3: Results

References

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Attached files

Name: 19NRM05_LPCT_UNIBO_temp_humidity.zip

Description: It contains 2 main folders:

- the first cycle accuracy test with humidity of 30%

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the second cycle accuracy test with humidity of 80% <p>Both cycle accuracy test contains 4 folders for each test temperature. In each of the 4 folders, there are 40 file “.txt”.</p> <p>The filename of a folder contains the following information: “acquisition_temperature_humidity”. Example: “4_20C_30” which stands for the fourth acquisition (during the cycle accuracy test) characterized by a temperature of 20 °C and a humidity of 30%.</p> <p>The filename of a “.txt” file contains the following information: “sensors_typeofsignal_temperature_humidity”. Example: “rog2_150Hz_20C_30%.txt” which stands for Rogowski number two tested with a sine wave of 150 Hz at a temperature of 20 °C and a humidity of 30%.</p> <p>Another example: “shunt_sinc_40C_30%.txt” which stands shunt resistor tested with sinc waveform at a temperature of 20 °C and a humidity of 30%.</p> <p>Each file “.txt” includes the raw samples acquired for 3 s with a sampling frequency of $f_s=50$ kHz.</p> <p>Each file contains 1 column and 150000 rows, elements of each row are separated by new line.</p>
<p>Agree to make the data public ? (yes/no)</p>	<p>yes</p>